

NECESSITY OF STUDYING POLITICAL LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: The article aimed at the studying of necessity and specific features of study of political linguistics is gaining a significant place all over the world. In the field of political linguistics, the study of political language requires a comprehensive knowledge of the history of this scientific direction, its current state, its interaction and influence with other scientific directions.

Keywords: formation, specific features, political linguistics, political context, discourse analysis, political communication.

Political linguistics is an interdisciplinary field combining linguistics and political science for a deeper understanding of the relationship between language and politics. The need to study political linguistics is seen in:

1. Allows you to analyze and understand political discourse, which is a means of influencing public opinion and forming political decisions. The analysis of political discourse helps to identify hidden motives and strategies that political leaders use to achieve their goals. The study of the language and rhetoric of political discourse allows us to identify nuances that can affect the perception of politics.

2. Develops the ability to think critically and analyze the presented information. We learn to understand argumentation and logical connections in political texts, analyze arguments and evaluate their validity. This helps us become critical-minded citizens and understand complex political issues.

3. It helps to better understand the cultural characteristics and values of various political communities. The language of politics reflects and shapes the ideological and cultural aspects of society. Understanding these aspects helps to create an effective communication strategy and establish a constructive dialogue with various political parties.

4. It also helps to develop effective communication skills. We will learn how to analyze and use various rhetorical strategies to confidently express our ideas and views. In addition, we are learning to adapt our communication to different audiences and contexts in order to be more successful in the political sphere.

5. An important aspect of the study of political linguistics is also the understanding of the influence of language on the formation of public opinion

and political rhetoric. We learn to recognize and analyze manipulative techniques in political communication, such as the use of emotional manipulation, the creation of stereotypes and the manipulative use of facts. This helps us to become more informed and critical consumers of information, as well as more effective communicators in the political sphere.

6. Provides a better understanding of the cultural and historical contexts of political debates and conflicts. We will learn how to analyze political texts. This helps us to better understand political processes and make informed decisions based on information analysis.

7. Allows you to develop effective communication skills.

Adapting communication to different audiences is important in the political sphere, where communication plays a key role in shaping public opinion and achieving political goals.

8. The study of political linguistics also contributes to the development of media analysis and information literacy skills. We are learning to recognize fake news, manipulation methods and biased information. This helps us to be more informed and critical consumers of information and protects us from manipulation and false information.

9. In addition, the study of political linguistics helps to better understand the cultural and social aspects of politics. We can study the linguistic features of various political systems and how they are reflected in language and communication. This helps us develop a broader and more diverse understanding of political processes and conflicts.

In general, the study of political linguistics gives us valuable tools and knowledge for analyzing and understanding the political field. This helps us develop critical thinking skills, effective communication and a deeper understanding of political processes. Moreover, the study of political linguistics can lead to the development of new approaches and strategies for political communication. It is possible to study how the use of specific language techniques and methods can improve the effectiveness of a political campaign or communication with voters. This can be especially useful for political consultants and strategists.

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